

Deployment and Assessment of Predictive Modelling, Environmentally Sustainable Digital Tools for Improving the Resilience of Inland Water-Way (IWW) Against Climate Change and Other Extremes

Anastasios Doulamis, Nikolaos Doulamis, Matthaios Bimpas, Ioannis Rallis, and Dimitrios Vamvatsikos

Abstract We increase the resilience of the Inland Water Ways (IWW) infrastructures and the connected land-infrastructures, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavorable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kind of hazards, a critical aspect towards resilience of these regions. Our main target is to combine downscaled climate change scenarios (applied to IWW infrastructures) with simulation tools and actual data to provide the relevant authorities/operators with integrated tools for more effective management of these infrastructures. Towards this direction, we aim to (a) use high resolution modelling data for the determination and the assessment of the climatic risk of on transport infrastructures and associated expected damages; (b) use existing data from various sources with new types of sensor-generated data (computer vision) to feed the used simulator; (c) utilize tailored weather forecasts for specific hot-spots, providing early warnings with corresponding impact assessment in real time; (d) develop improved multi-temporal, multi-sensor Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV)- and satellite-based observations with robust spectral analysis, computer vision and machine learning-based assessment for diverse transport infrastructures; (e) design and implement an integrated Resilience Assessment Platform environment as an innovative planning tool that permit a quantitative resilience assessment through an end-to-end simulation environment; and (f) design and implement a Common Operational Picture, including an enhanced visualization interface and an Incident Management. This research fills the gap of the current practice where manual inspection is often used for managing the IWW infrastructures. Our approach is designed under a generic way to be applicable to other land uses and civil infrastructures like rural/urban regions monitoring, freight management over rivers, and environmental inspec-

A. Doulamis (✉) · N. Doulamis · M. Bimpas · I. Rallis · D. Vamvatsikos
National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece
e-mail: adoulam@cs.ntua.gr

tion of Natura areas. Our platform aims to address multi-hazard risk understanding, smart prevention and preparedness, as well as faster, adapted and efficient response.

1 Introduction

Every year, 108 trillion tonne-kilometers of products are transported worldwide, of which the majority is borne by sea (70%), 18% is handled by rail, 9% is carried by road, 2% is shipped on inland waterways, and about 0.25% is transported by air [1]. In 2020, road transport accounted for 75.3% of the total inland freight transport and its share has been consistently rising over the last decade. In 2020, more than 10.3 million workers were employed in the freight industry (including warehousing and supporting transport activities), which accounted for 5.3% of the overall EU-27 labour force [2]. Freight transport and logistics are vital to the EU's Single Market, and for Europe's prosperity. Additionally, a well-performing and dynamic freight and logistics sectors improve overall productivity and competitiveness through job growth, economies of scale, and by generating remarkable economic and social added value [3]. Figures reveal that about EUR 599 billion, or around 5% of the EU's Gross Domestic Product, has been created by the transport and logistics industry, with over EUR 931 billion spent by private household on transport-related goods (13% of total consumption), and more than 1.15 million companies active in transportation and logistics [4]. This impact is also internationally recognized. Indeed, the annual World Bank International Logistics Performance Index ranks no less than 13 European economies in the top 20 of global leaders in logistics [5].

Global freight traffic is anticipated to triple for inland modes in the next 30 years [6]. In addition, in the EU, surface freight traffic is expected to rise by 53% by 2050 [7]. However, the biggest concern is how economic gains from increased demand can be sustained when taking into account adverse externalities and possible rebound effects. Transport modes still adhere to silo mentality, despite ports setting moderate goals on transport modal split. Other major challenges include saturated infrastructure, carbon emission goals, and energy constraints [8].

This paper leverages existing tools and services (e.g., climate models, modelling of extreme events and their impacts, Early Warning Systems (EWS), environmental monitoring sensors and EU services, such as Copernicus), emerging solutions (including Nature-based Solutions—NBS—, and digital tools, e.g., water, terrestrial and satellite imaging, Machine Learning (ML) and enhanced data fusion techniques, etc.) in order to develop an integrated planning platform that can be primarily applied to Inland Waterways (IWW) infrastructures. Our platform aims to address multi-hazard risk understanding, smart prevention and preparedness, as well as faster, adapted and efficient response. Our proposed new integrated system to support operational and strategic adaptation and mitigation measures, by better absorbing and efficiently recovering from CC impacts (including extreme events), aims to

increase the resilience of IWW. The deployed technical, social, and institutional measures are first simulated by our Digital Twin system and then installed and demonstrated in order to be assessed against economic and other type of indicators.

2 Previous Works and Originality—Beyond the State-of-the-Art

Regarding the effective management of IWW and connected hinterland infrastructures, the current assessment of likely needs, as a crisis evolves, is currently limited to individual decision makers, each acting within a specific domain of knowledge [9]. Instead, our approach entails forming an overall dynamical picture of a disaster as it develops, forecasting quantitatively need indicators in time and supplying these forecasts with reliability measures. Concerning modelling tools and simulators that can be used for increasing the resilience of the IWW, the currently available climatic and atmospheric indicators for CC scenarios are not directly applicable for impact assessment on IWW and the integrated land infrastructure [10]. On the contrary, in this paper identifies an optimal set of quantitative primary parameters and impact indicators in order to quantify CC impacts on IWW accounting for specific categories of Hazards, encompassing climate extreme, hydrological and soil quality as well as structural stress indicators. An analysis of climatic models and their consequences on environmental parameters is performed, according to a reliability-based approach of durability in order to define the needed parameters and their sensitivity, for instance mean plus variation of the temperature over a year when considering carbonation.

Another limitation of the current works in the overall monitoring process of the IWW systems is the fact that they are relied on limited sensorial data [11]. In the design phase, environmental actions are taken from relevant standards with no provisions for the effects of CC [12]. Instead, in our research approach the integration of monitoring information from new technologically advanced sensors (e.g., computer vision, incl. hyperspectral and multispectral cameras, etc.) besides traditional methods allow for significantly improved system identification and consequently more accurate vulnerability assessment.

3 Main Technological Pillars

3.1 *Climate, Atmospheric Forcing, and Multi-hazard Modelling*

Our methodology can be summed up as follows: (a) Dynamical downscaling of representative high-resolution environmental data to map relevant risks at site scale; (b) Risk assessment based on analysis of the interactions among IWW and

meteorological, hydrological and climatic parameters with the utilization of the multiscale two-ways coupled atmospheric, oceanic and soil models [13]; (c) Assessment of environmental impacts on IWW vulnerability and resilience related to variations of various climate and environmental parameters via the utilization of an advanced land surface model; (d) Operational evaluation, verification and validation based on monitoring data including uncertainty quantification; (e) Pre-event analysis, planning and training of responsible stakeholders, including best practice guidelines; (f) Statistical analysis of the stochastic climatic events as they have been recorded, for return level assessment.

3.2 Multi-hazard Vulnerability Modules and Assessment Toolkit for IWW and Assets

A Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Assessment Toolkit (MHVAT) software suite is developed to offer integrated analytical assessment of the vulnerability of IWW under natural (climate change induced) or/and man-made hazards, as well as mixed hazard (e.g., levee effect in dike-protected floodplains). It uses stochastic simulation techniques to assess the performance of IWW under scenarios of single, cotemporaneous and cascading events, integrating information from hazard to structural response and risk/vulnerability assessment. Degraded states of IWW and non-direct IWW elements/assets (i.e., integrated assets to the hinterland) are considered to incorporate corrosion and ageing. Output performance metrics encompass the estimation of direct losses, functionality (reduced speed/weight of vehicles while repairs last, lane closure, etc.) and time-to-restore functionality (downtime) as repairs are effected. The MHVAT is employed to produce Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules (MHVM) of software that characterize all types of IWW elements. Each MHVM incorporates a surrogate model for rapidly updating and re-assessing the vulnerability and functionality of the various IWW elements. The MHVM forms the basis of the IWAT platform, interrogating hazard simulators, handling queries and passing on information on component states to enable reliable pre-event assessment and near-real-time post-event reassessment of system performance.

3.3 Improved Computer Vision Techniques and Machine Learning Techniques

In our system, the proposed Computer Vision (CV) tools initially apply image processing methods to identify features that should be invariant under “affine distortions” (transformations) and then implement heuristic approaches so as to remove outliers and man-made artificial structures that often exist in IWW, which can be confused with defects. In the sequel, we use novel Machine Learning (ML)

algorithms that enable the generalization of the extracted patterns to video recordings of IWW outside the training dataset. In addition, deep ML is incorporated to automatically find more complex feature structures through the exploitation, for instance, of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), so as to improve the identification accuracy. Our target is to provide the relevant IWW authorities and operators with in-depth inspection of their infrastructure, speedily and reliably, without interfering with the traffic and endangering the inspectors or/and the commuters.

3.4 Remote Sensing, Including Quick Assessment Damage Maps

In case of a significant disaster event, damage maps are generated through Copernicus EMS, based on high-resolution satellite images. Those maps, but also actual satellite images where available, are used to carry out a fast and synoptic wide-area assessment and identify extensive damage, flooding, landslide blockage etc. As shown, the map gives a valuable synoptic overview (water origin and extent, overall landslide size etc.), but lacks local detail, which the our system can provide. In such situations the fixed sensors may be compromised, and other type of vehicles cannot easily access all sites (in a fast and safe manner); hence locally controlled remote sensing is needed.

3.5 Fore-Now/Casting Weather Predictions Methods and Tools

The adopted approach also applies weather fore- and now-casting methods at such high resolution to allow for an accurate assessment of the impact of the models on the IWW supporting reliable decisions and appropriate mitigation strategies. We use EWS to anticipate extreme weather events and their impact on the IWW and connected networks. The EWS uses all available local weather information (rain gauges, stream gauges, automatic weather stations, weather radars observations, etc.) and forecasts (short-term forecasts—Now-casts). The various observations are blended using geo-statistical techniques [14] and the different sources of forecasts merged [15] (taking into account the related uncertainty of each source of information) with the aim of obtaining the optimal hazard forecast/impact information at each lead-time at the identified hot-spots of the IWW. Information on the uncertainty is also calculated, when possible, to help the decision making in the DSS. Figure 1 shows the approach adopted for weather predictions.

Fig. 1 Weather observations and forecasts/impact products which are used

4 The Middleware Module

Our middleware acts as a broker across network communication interfaces to ensure that each connected service and information system delivers its information to the appropriate format to the developed platform or other IWW information systems. The middleware consist of (1) *Abstraction layer* in which the information from different sources is available in the same format. (2) *Resources Management Framework/Fusion* that provides components for storing, retrieving and managing metadata and data as well as for filtering, aggregation, and fusion of data; (3) *Event management, filtering and contextual information modules* that handle all the events from the data sources and categorize retrieved events and information to proper categories; (4) *Semantic representation layer* creates a base layer of common/standardized way of knowledge of the different IWW related resources/information with the proper metrics to be organized and create the connection between that info; (5) *Communication management module* in which all the appropriate interfaces/protocols for the communication with the different data sources exists; (6) *Security and privacy module* that tackles with data and identity security and privacy aspects and (7) *Data Fusion*. This module implements the pre-processing analysis and the data fusion techniques.

5 The Assessment Tools—IWAT

5.1 The Integrated IWW Assessment Tool

This tool undertakes the integration and chaining of the hazard analysis and simulation tools, the various vulnerability functions and analysis including the MHVM, the traffic simulators used by the IWW operators as well as all additional socio-economic impact analysis providing the simulation environment to run end-to-end impact/resilience assessment scenarios for the test cases either in pre-event assessment of IWW risk or near-real-time post-event reassessment of the evolving IWW risk as sensor information is integrated into the system. The methodology that are used for the implementation of is the following: (a) Estimate the intensity of various

hazards on IWW elements; (b) Estimate the expected damages and associated direct losses in monetary and functionality terms; (c) Express the component loss-of-functionality to expected traffic disruptions; (d) Estimate the overall socioeconomic impact of traffic disruptions; (e) Estimate the overall impact and risk in terms of cost for all scenarios (direct structural and indirect impact/cost); (f) Identify interrelationships of IWW elements and assess their impact; (g) Test various risk management approaches, plans and strategies, countermeasures and adaptations; (h) Understand the sensitivity of system assets, infrastructure, and services to the selected types of hazards/events towards a performance based planning; (i) Set up risk-based response strategies adapted to scenarios and define efficient standard response procedures and (j) Assess the overall resilience of IWW under a holistic quantitative approach.

5.2 *Enhanced Visualization Common Operational Picture (COP), Incident Management System (IMS), and Decision Support System (DSS)*

All COP functionalities are integrated to enable enhanced situational awareness capabilities to the IWW operators. The previous tool, as a part of the COP, provides direct access to the predefined “what-if” scenarios as described above, providing risk-based planning capabilities, risk management, mitigation solutions, and adaptation strategies propositions. This way we enable the operators to assess in real-time the expected damages and identify possible expected impacts, providing thus the unique capability to initiate efficient response actions, right after (in case of now-cast data) or even before (in case of forecast data) the occurrence of the catastrophic event providing early situational awareness. The response actions follow predefined patterns according to the Standard Response Procedures developed during the “what-if” scenarios process to save valuable response time and enable coordinated response (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 IMS, risk/impact assessment simulation and 3D COP representation in a unified environment

5.3 IWW Digital Twin

The IWW Digital Twin (DT) is built a data representation of assets, processes, and systems in the IWW built and natural environment. It uses ML to understand and learn from the behavior of the system over time and predict the location and time of future flooding, or drought. It learns the behaviors of each IWW element, the relationships between them and how different conditions (e.g., environmental parameters) impact them [16]. The development methodology is as follows: To start, reality modelling and 3D mapping software is used to generate a high-resolution 3D mesh by using overlapping photos from drones and ground-level imagery. The model include digital terrain data, which is fundamental for any hydrological simulation. The DT is continuously refreshed from multiple sources—such as sensors, continuous surveying, or GIS updates—to represent current conditions. One of the primary uses of the DT is the simulation of what-if scenarios that show the impact of flooding on IWW navigation, for different types of vessels.

6 Conclusions

This paper develops an integrated intelligent platform for assessing, deploying and predictive modelling of environmentally sustainable tools for improving the resilience of Inland Water Way (IWW) against climate change and other extremes. We combine downscaled climate change scenarios (applied to IWW infrastructures) with simulation tools and actual data to assist local authorities and responsible persons for the IWWs towards a more effective management of these infrastructures. This effective management is carried out by the use of high resolution modelling tools, sensor-generated data, innovative computer vision techniques and machine learning algorithms, remote sensing analysis, weather forecasts and modelling and resilience tools. Visualization methods and decision support algorithms are also supported.

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References

1. OECD – International Transport Forum (2019) ITF Transport Outlook 2019, p 38
2. European Commission (2020) EU transport in figures, Statistical pocketbook 2020, p 25
3. EC (2007) The EU’s freight transport agenda: boosting the efficiency, integration and sustainability of freight transport in Europe, p 2
4. EC (2020) EU transport in figures – Statistical pocketbook 2020, p 21
5. World Bank (2018) Connecting to Compete – 2018 Trade Logistics in the Global Economy: The Logistics Performance Index and Its Indicators, p 12

6. OECD – International Transport Forum (2019) ITF Transport Outlook 2019, p 39
7. European Commission (2018) In-depth analysis in support of Commission Communication COM(2018) 773 – ‘A Clean Planet for all: A European long-term strategic vision for a prosperous, modern, competitive and climate neutral economy’, p 82
8. Ugarte GM, Golden JS, Dooley K (2016) Lean versus green: the impact of lean logistics on greenhouse gas emissions in consumer goods supply chains. *J Purchasing Supply Manag* 22:98–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pursup.2015.09.002>
9. Storms K (2025) Unravelling D&D within the maritime ecosystem and its influence on IWT in port-hinterland supply chains. Diss. University of Antwerp
10. Donnelly J, Abolfathi S, Pearson J, Chatrabgoun O, Daneshkhah A (2022) Gaussian process emulation of spatio-temporal outputs of a 2D inland flood model. *Water Res* 225:11910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.119100>
11. Li S, Negenborn RR, Lodewijks G (2013) Survey on planning problems in inland waterway transport: Current status and future perspectives. In: 16th International IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), pp 1231–1237
12. Calderón-Rivera N, Bartusevičienė I, Ballini F (2024) Barriers and solutions for sustainable development of inland waterway transport: a literature review. *Transp Econ Manag* 2:31–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.team.2024.01.001>
13. Maronga B et al (2015) The parallelized large-eddy simulation model (palm) version 4.0 for atmospheric and oceanic flows: model formulation, recent developments, and future perspectives. *Geosci Model Dev* 8:1539–1637. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-2515-2015>
14. Berndt C, Rabiei E, Haberlandt U (2014) Geostatistical merging of rain gauge and radar data for high temporal resolutions and various station density scenarios. *J Hydrol* 508:88–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2013.10.028>
15. Kober K, Craig GC, Keil C, Dörnbrack A (2012) Blending a probabilistic nowcasting method with a high resolution numerical weather prediction ensemble for convective precipitation forecasts. *QJR Meteorol Soc* 138:755–768. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.939>
16. Yfantis V, Kavoura A, Ntalianis, K (2025) Business digital twin – a crucial tool for the public sector during human-made disasters. In: Kavoura A, Briciu V, Briciu A (Eds) Strategic innovative marketing and tourism –creative solutions and digital transformation challenges – 11th ICSIMAT, Brasov, Romania, 2024. <https://link.springer.com/book/9783031819612#accessibility-information>

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